

CLINICAL EFFICACY OF GROPRINOSIN IN CHILDREN WITH CHRONIC TONSILLITIS ASSOCIATED WITH EPSTEIN BARR VIRUS

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Relevance Chronic tonsillitis is one of the main problems of otolaryngology and pediatrics and accounts for 74% according to some authors. [1]. The cause of chronic tonsillitis is more often a viral infection, which is later replaced by a bacterial one [2]. According to modern data, chronic tonsillitis is a polyetiological disease, in the genesis of which numerous factors play a role, but the cause of inflammatory process aggravation in pharynx more often is the effect of microorganisms. The main pathogens are Streptococcus α -haemolyticus, β -haemolyticus, γ -haemolyticus, Staphylococcus aureus, CNS Staphylococcus, Neisseria spp., Haemophilus spp, Corynebacterium spp, Candida fungi [3].

Currently, many studies are devoted to Epstein-Barr virus (EBV) in the development of various inflammatory diseases, including chronic tonsillitis [4]. Immune disorders in chronic tonsillitis are complex, they concern both cellular and humoral immunity, entail the aggravation of the course, the frequency of complications of the disease.

Objective of the investigation: to study clinical efficacy of Groprinosin in children with chronic tonsillitis associated with Epstein Barr virus.

Materials and methods of investigation. General clinical methods of investigation, pharyngoscopy were carried out to the patients. All patients had a pharyngeal swab for microflora and sensitivity to antibiotics, as well as Epstein-Barr virus DNA was determined by PCR. The number of diseased children was 36 children, aged 4 to 6 years.

Results and discussion. Chronic tonsillitis was detected in 36 of 135 patients with chronic tonsillitis: Control group 1 - 16 children received the standard therapy; Group 2 - the main group - 20 children received Groprinosin in suppositories in the dosage of 150,000 2 times daily for 5 days besides the standard therapy. During the treatment no side effects of Groprinosin were observed.

In children with chronic tonsillitis in the first two days of the exacerbation of the disease who received Groprinosin reduced the duration of clinical symptoms compared with the control group. Temperature increase was noted in all examined patients. Temperature decreased on the 3rd day in the majority of patients in the control group, on the 2nd day in the main group. In 95% of the

children in the main group the pain in the throat disappeared on the 3rd day, while in the control group (87%) the children noted pain in the throat on the 5th-6th day. Pharyngoscopy in both groups before therapy was characterized by the same type of changes - swelling, hyperemia of the pharyngeal mucosa and caseous plaques in the lacunae. After standard therapy in the control group these changes have disappeared on the 8th day from the disease onset, while in children of the main group these changes have been eliminated on the 4th day in 89% of children and in 11% of children on the 5th day.

Conclusions. Combined application of Groprinosin together with standard therapy promoted more essential positive dynamics of clinical parameters and pharyngoscopic picture of chronic tonsillitis associated with Epstein Barr virus. The use of Groprinosin did not cause any side effects in the patients.

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